

NAMED ENTITY RECOGNITION IN TURKISH USING ASSOCIATION MEASURES

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ABSTRACT

Named Entity Recognition which is an important subject of Natural Language Processing is a key technology of information extraction, information retrieval, question answering and other text processing applications. In this study, we evaluate previously well-established association measures as an initial attempt to extract two-worded named entities in a Turkish corpus. Furthermore we propose a new association measure, and compare it with the other methods. The evaluation of these methods is performed by precision and recall measures.

KEYWORDS

Turkish, Point-wise Mutual Information, Mutual Dependency, First Kulczynski, Joint Probability

1. INTRODUCTION

Named Entity Recognition (NER) aims to locate and classify named entities in an unstructured text. NER classify elements in text into predefined categories such as the names of persons, organizations, locations etc. NER systems serves as an important pre-processing system for tasks such as information extraction, information retrieval, question answering and other text processing applications.

In NER systems, linguistic grammar-based techniques and/or statistical models have been used. Although grammar-based systems typically obtain better precision, these systems have lower recall and generally they are not independent of language. On the other hand, statistical NER systems require a large amount of manually annotated training data.

There has been a lot of work on NER systems on several languages especially on English. Although new models and techniques have been suggested, developing NER systems for Turkish is still a difficult process because of the agglutinative structure of the language.

In this study, we evaluate previously well-established association measures in order to extract two-worded named entities in Turkish corpus. The association measures are simply used to evaluate the relations between two or more items in a given set. We assume that the words in

multi-worded named entities have such strong ties that these words tend to co-occur frequently. The methods/measures implemented in the study are based on point-wise mutual information [1], log frequency biased mutual dependency [2], first Kulczynski [3] and joint probability. Additionally, a new association measure is proposed and compared with other techniques.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 summarizes previous related work. Section 3 describes association measures, presents base set, and explains the experiments. Section 4 reports results, and concludes with further future work.

2. RELATED WORK

In the 1990s, the name entity recognition was firstly described in the Message Understanding Conference (MUC), which was sponsored by the US Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA). One of the first research papers in the field was presented by Lisa F. Rau [4]. Since then, many methods and strategies for automatic identification of named entities have been proposed. Methods for NER systems classify into 3 groups: the rule based approach, probabilistic approach, and the hybrid approach.

In the rule-based approach, the natural language descriptions and rules need to be formulated. The rules are used to define name entities using their syntactic and lexical structure with the help of manually annotated corpora. In addition to rules, rule-based approaches require gazetteers and general dictionary [5]. Differently from rule-based approach, the probabilistic approach does not require any natural language information. This approach builds their models by learning patterns from the annotated corpora [5]; and the approach displays good enough performance with large corpora ([6][7]). In [8] it is indicated that recent studies about NER are mostly based on probabilistic methods.

Although some studies address language independence or multilingualism in NER solutions, a large part of the NER studies are on English. NER studies on other languages than English have been also carried out; such as German ([9]) Spanish ([10]), Japanese ([11][12][13]), Chinese ([14] [15][16]), French ([17][18]), Greek ([19]), Italian ([20][21]), Bulgarian ([22]), Hindi ([23]), Polish ([24]), Russian ([25]), Swedish ([26]), Portuguese ([27]).

There is a limited work on NER systems applied on Turkish texts. To our best knowledge, the study of Cucerzan and Yarowski ([22]) is the first study on Turkish NER. In [22], a language independent bootstrapping algorithm that learns from word internal and contextual information of entities is presented and the proposed algorithm is experimented on five languages including Turkish. Following this, in [28] a statistical approach (HMMs) for NER is used on Turkish texts. In [29], a huge database of person, organization, and location names is constructed instead of employing a complex name entity extraction scheme. As a recent study, Kucuk and Yazici [30] presented a rule-based NER system for Turkish.

3. EXPERIMENTS

3.1. Methods: Association Measures

In this section, detailed information about the proposed method and other competing methods; point-wise mutual information, log frequency biased mutual dependency, First Kulczynski and joint probability; are given.

Point-wise mutual information (*PMI*) is the association measure which generates a score depending on the mutual dependence of the two or more words. For two words x and y occurring consecutively in the corpus the *PMI* may be given as

$$PMI(xy) = \log_2 \frac{P(xy)}{P(x) * P(y)} \quad (1)$$

$P(x)$, $P(y)$ are the probabilities of the words x and y appearing separately respectively. $P(xy)$ is the probability of x and y coming together.

Log frequency biased mutual dependency (MD) is a derived measure of mutual information ([31]). MD may be formulized for the words x and y as

$$MD(xy) = \log \frac{P(xy)^2}{P(x) * P(y)} + \log P(xy) \quad (2)$$

First Kulczynski (FK) gives a measure for association between two consecutive words in the corpus. FK for the words x and y is presented as

$$FK(xy) = \frac{f(xy)}{f(x\bar{y}) + f(\bar{x}y)} \quad (3)$$

where $f(xy)$ is the co-occurrence frequency of the words x and y . $f(x\bar{y})$ is the frequency of x followed by any word other than y . $f(\bar{x}y)$ is the occurrence frequency of y not preceded by x .

Joint probability (JP) is the probability of the words x and y to occur together in the corpus ($P(xy)$) and the method is accepted to be the easiest way to score the associations between words in a text.

The idea behind the proposed method (PM) in the study may be given as follows

“If the words x and y compose a two-word named-entity, the number of separate occurrences of x and y ($f(x)$ and $f(y)$ respectively) must be close or equal to the number of co-occurrences of the words; $f(xy)$; together.”

The proposed method measures the distance of separate frequencies of words ($f(x)$ and $f(y)$) from the co-occurrence frequency ($f(xy)$). The distances for the first and the second words are squared and summed to generate a single score for each named-entity candidate. The method is formulized below.

$$PM(xy) = \left(\frac{f(xy) - 1}{f(x) - 1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{f(xy) - 1}{f(y) - 1} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

3.2. Base Set

The experiment is utilized on Bilkent corpus which is compiled in Bilkent University for linguistics studies [28]. In the study, a base set is generated from the corpus as in [32]. The base set is constructed by merging the best 200 candidates from the ranked lists of competing association measures. The base set is re-ranked by each method and the ranked lists are used to evaluate the performance of each method.

3.3. Evaluation

The evaluation of competing methods is performed by precision and recall measures. The precision is simply the proportion of true named-entities to the total number of candidates in the set. The recall is the proportion of true named-entities to the total number of true named-entities in the base set. Instead of giving a single score of precision and recall for the whole set or any

proportion of the set, we plot curves of precision and recall in order to present scores for any proportions of the whole set.

4. RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

The implementation of association measures on the Bilkent corpus has returned a base set of 569 two-worded candidates. The base set involves 32.34% true named-entities of two words. Figure 1 gives the precision curves for the competing methods: *PMI*, *MD*, *FK* and *JP*.

Figure 1. Precision curves of association measures in named entity recognition

It is observed from Figure 1 that any of the methods including the proposed method does not perform consistently better than the other. It is also seen that in the first ~10% percent of the base set, all the methods generate non-consistent precision values; between 20% and %40 proportions of the set the proposed method generates higher scores. In the range 40%-80%, the curves of mutual dependency and point-wise mutual information dominate the others. It is noteworthy that joint probability is the method which gives worst results in named-entity recognition.

Figure 2 depicts recall curves for the methods. Recall curves show that the competing methods except joint probability and first Kulczynski generate similar results of recall meaning that none of the methods retrieve true entities faster than others.

Figure 2. Recall curves of association measures in named entity recognition

5. CONCLUSIONS

As a conclusion, the attempt to evaluate several association measures including the proposed measure on named entity recognition showed that current association measures do not succeed in the complete base set. Since point-wise mutual information, mutual dependency and the proposed method achieve in several proportions of base set, we believe that if these methods are modified, some improvement in the results may be achieved.

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